

SOCIO-CULTURAL NOTIONS OF GENDER DYNAMICS IN LINGUISTIC RESEARCHES

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada gender dinamikasi tushunchasi va uning mohiyati yoritib berilgan. Shuningdek, uning ijtimoiy-madaniy munosabatlardagi voqelanishi ham asoslab berilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: genger, dinamika, gender dinamikasi, ijtimoiy-madaniy, gender meyorlari, linguistic tadqiqotlar, nutq tahlili, ijtimoiy munosabatlar, nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar.

Аннотация. В данной статье объясняется понятие гендерной динамики и ее сущность. Также обосновывается его возникновение в социокультурных отношениях.

Ключевые слова: гендер, динамика, гендерная динамика, социокультурные, гендерные нормы, лингвистические исследования, дискурс-анализ, социальные отношения, теоретико-практические исследования.

Annotation. This article explains the concept of gender dynamics and its essence. Also, its occurrence in socio-cultural relations is justified.

Key words: gender, dynamics, gender dynamics, socio-cultural, gender norms, linguistic research, discourse analysis, social relations, theoretical and practical research

Language is considered to be a social event which has been developing through the evolution of society and human beings in it. Every new item of the scientific or social advance can cause to the changes which language has been come across during the centuries. The study of language and gender together has increasingly become a matter of linguistic researches. Although phonological, lexical, grammatical and other types of linguistic analysis still maintain their prestige in the field of interdisciplinary research, the gender issues have always been a central approach to linguistic researches. The process has also led to the creation of new linguistic concepts, ideas and research works which deal with specific problems and questions related to linguistic speech analysis and gender. In this article, gender dynamics is analyzed as one of the new concepts of the gender linguistics. In the meantime, we have to define what is dynamics itself? Dynamics is put into words with following definitions:

1. physics: a branch of mechanics that deals with forces and their relation primarily to the motion but sometimes also to the equilibrium of bodies.

2. a pattern or process of change, growth, or activity population dynamics
3. variation and contrast in force or intensity (as in music)

Also, dynamics is regarded to be the forces or properties which stimulate growth, development, or change within a system or process "the dynamics of changing social relations".

As gender linguistics focuses on the issues and questions which are relevant to the gender and linguistics at the same time, gender dynamics can be a concept of it. Afterwards, we should clarify the meaning of gender dynamics by connecting to the common definitions of the original term "dynamics".

Gender dynamics refers to relationships and interactions between people based on gender. Gender dynamics is identified by socio-cultural perceptions of gender and the relationship of power that determines them. Depending on their manifestation, gender dynamics may reinforce or oppose existing norms (e.g., gender norm reinforcement may say that men can only look at women at home and with the child; and objecting to gender norms is normal. means that the situation. women).

During the centuries, misunderstandings about the gender issues are observed in the theoretical and applied researches which persuaded listeners to have a wrong conceptual image. This misconception has reflected that gender issues on society are only up to the sex or sexual communications, conditions between men and women or girls and boys. However, different attitudes to the gender problems by linguistics could have changed the fixed scope on the issue, and they created new research topics of the gender in language. According to the approaches, we can identify accurate distinctions between sex and gender as followings.

Most of people tend to use the terms "sex" and "gender" simultaneously, but this is incorrect. Sex and gender are different, and it is prominent issue to understand why.

"Sex" indicates the physical and biological differences between people who are male, female. A person typically has their sex assigned at birth based on physiological characteristics. A person's sex is typically based on certain biological factors, such as their reproductive organs, genes, and hormones.

Gender, on the other hand, involves how a person identifies. Unlike natural sex, gender is not made up of binary forms. Gender also exists as social constructs — as gender "roles" or "norms." These are defined as the socially constructed roles, behaviors, and attributes that a society considers appropriate for men and women. Gender refers to the socially constructed characteristics of women and

men, such as norms, roles, and relationships of and between groups of women and men. It varies from society to society, and can be changed adapting to the place and time. Gender roles in some societies are more rigid than in others. However, these are not always set in stone, and roles and stereotypes can shift over time.

A person's gender is how they identify internally and how they express this externally. People may use clothing, appearances, and behaviors to express the gender that they identify with. However, gender is not neatly divided along the binary lines of "man" and "woman."

For centuries, many societies have enforced the notion that a person is either a man or woman based on their physical characteristics. This idea conflates sex and gender, which is incorrect. Sex and gender are not the same. In general terms, sex refers to a person's physical characteristics at birth, and gender encompasses a person's identities, expressions, and societal roles.

A person may identify with a gender that is different from their natal sex or with no gender at all. The latter identity is often referred to as nonbinary, but this is an umbrella term that covers many identifications.

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